

Principals' Fund Generation Strategies for Effective Administration of Public Junior Secondary School in Rivers State

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Abstract

The study investigated principals' fund generation strategy for effective administration of public junior secondary schools in Rivers State. The study adopted a descriptive survey design. The population of this study was 351 principals (251 male principals and 100 female principals of all the public junior secondary schools in Rivers State. The sample size for this study comprised of (251 male and 100 female principals) of all the public junior secondary schools in Rivers State. The instrument for the study was titled "Principals' Fund Generation Strategy for Effective Administration Questionnaire" (PFMSEAQ). The reliability of the questionnaire instrument was established through Cronbach Alpha Method. It yielded co-efficient of 0.84. This result therefore showed internal consistency of the test items. Mean and standard deviation was used to analyze the data and answer the research questions, while z-test statistics was used to test the hypothesis at 0.5 significant levels. The agreement or disagreement of any of the item depended on the criterion mean, which are 2.50. The findings revealed that the principals fund generation strategy is achieving moderate extent in public junior secondary schools in Rivers State it will be difficult for principals to achieve high performance in schools for lack of funding. Based on the findings of the study the researcher recommended that principals' should collaborate with community stakeholders to initiate sources of fund to enhance the achievement of school goals and objectives.

Keywords: Fund generation strategy, effective administration

INTRODUCTION

Education, in general is considered expensive because it demands both material and human resources for the attainment of goals/objectives. Secondary education financing in Nigeria had serious challenges that many researchers had proffered some remedies. Money is the obvious and important element in the success of all educational ventures in which secondary education is not left out. However, secondary education is that level of education which children receive after primary education and before tertiary level (Federal Republic of Nigeria, 2013). Oyewole (2006) observed that the principal is the chief executive officer in secondary school in Nigeria. He further noted that the principal performs a good number of administrative functions in his/her effort to achieve goals and objectives which the school is meant to achieve especially in fund generation. Fund generation function of the school principal involves sourcing for fund locally and managing fund for his school, securing adequate revenue from government through other sources and managing expenditure. The financial management tasks of school principal according to Eziuzo (2014) include preparation of budget, securing revenue for the school internally and use of the fund at his disposal prudently.

Internally generated funds, according to Asodike (2014) are the revenue raised by the school internally to supplement grant allocation from government, but the scope of fund raising varies from one school to another, such internal sources of school funds include: enlisting help of local community, Parent Teachers Association (PTA) levies, proceeds:- from drama club; cultural dance groups; from sales of agricultural produce; from poultry/pig keeping; from sales of crafts/arts and from renting of school facilities. The money realized from internal sources constitute large sum which demand the financial expertise of school principal to manage in order to boost the school financial base. Normally, every student termly pays the PTA levy which is managed by the school authority in conjunction with the PTA officials. In many cases, PTA money is used in providing PTA teachers and some school facilities and repairs. Apart from provision of both

human and material resources, PTA motivates both students and teachers by giving awards and scholarships to exceptional students and teachers. This goes a long way to encourage hard work and commitment in the school.

Ogbonnaya (2000) asserted that the main purpose of financial management is the raising of funds and ensuring that the funds realized are utilized in the most effective and efficient manner. The argument is that funds or resources are scarce and that all efforts should be made by educational administrators and planners to ensure optimal utilization of fund. However, financial management is the fundamental element on which the success of any organization depends. Bua and Adzongo (2014) posited that poor management of fund in schools, results in; financial misappropriation, embezzlement, diversion of finance to personal issue use and negligence in school finance matters, especially issues on mismanagement of internally raised funds impacted on school financial base negatively. So generating money internally and managing same efficiently by the school head can result in improved finance for the school. Some of the sources through which fund is generated in schools includes:

1. **Proceeds from School Activities:** School activities represent another good source of financing public secondary schools. They include such activities as sales of students hand crafts, sales of books and stationery, staging of school plays and raffles, sales of farm products from the school farm, funds raising activity can be organized by the school authority where parents could be invited to raise money for school projects. Appeal fund raising. The school authority could appeal in writing to wealthy persons in the community where the school is located for financial assistance in order to develop their school. This practice if well-articulated could yield good results in Rivers State.
2. **Use of Direct Labour:** The Chief executive can make use of direct labour in carrying out school projects in order to reduce expenses instead of using contractors. In most cases students can also be used especially the big boys when the job does not require experts to execute. This is a good source of financing education.
3. **Payment for Extra Lesson:** School principals could organize extra lessons for students after the official school hours. The proceeds could be used to do some works in the school by the school authority after compensating the teachers for their extra efforts.
4. **Community Involvement:** The school administrator cannot successfully run the school in isolation without the involvement of members of the community. The community will help the school in carrying out its policies especially in the area of discipline and settlement of disputes involving both the students, staff and community. The community could be used to supply both free and cheap labour to the school if cordial relationship exists between the school and the community. Donation. A good school principal who has a good relationship with the community will be able to attract both financial and material donations from the people of the community where his school is located including scholarships, to his students. The principal should know when and how to organize fund raising in his school so as to get people's donations to his school.
5. **Old Student's Association:** Effective use of the Old Students' Association by the school authority is always very helpful and healthy to the school. This association normally provides both cash and materials for the growth and development of their alma-mater. Every good school principal utilizes this source to finance his school. Ogbonnaya (2000), states that nongovernmental organization is an association registered under the societies registration act, public trust act and the companies act with general body, executive, paid staff and volunteers. Since the financing of education is a joint responsibility and involves the private sector, a good school administrator must avail himself the opportunity of involving any of the NGOs in the state in funding his school in any form. Osei-Owusu and Kwame (2015), stated that education could be funded by means of endowments. While UBE (2012) believed that the payment of landed property tax should be one of the reliable sources of funding secondary education. Furthermore, UBE, (2012) opined that education could be financed through the following sources: Educational levy, Donations, Rentals, Old Students financial assistance, Registration fees.

Statement of the Problem

Principals are saddled with several administrative functions. Out of the lots, the operational function of generating funds for the secondary schools. There has been a lot report of lack of fund and inability of principals to initiate fund generation mechanism for secondary schools in Rivers State. These problems are yet to be addressed in secondary schools. They are noted to be most of the reasons why the secondary schools in Rivers State are not performing up to expectation.

In view of the above, community stakeholders are worried over these challenges. They said that it is capable of reducing level of productivity. The researcher is therefore worried about the extent to which the principals are generating fund internally in secondary schools. To this end, this study sought to analyzes the extent school principals' are generating fund in secondary schools in Rivers State.

Objective of the Study

The aim and objective of this study was to find out Principals' fund generation strategy for effective administration of public junior secondary schools in Rivers State. In. specific terms, the objective of the study were to:

Determine the extent principals adopt fund generation strategy for effective administration of public Junior Secondary Schools in Rivers State.

Research Questions

The following questions guided the study.

What is the extent of generation of fund strategy for effective administration of public junior secondary schools in Rivers State?

Hypothesis

The following hypotheses were tested at 0.05 alpha level of significance.

There is no significant difference between male and female principals in their mean ratings in the extent of fund generation strategy for effective administration of public junior secondary schools in Rivers State.

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted a descriptive survey design. The population of this study was 351 principals (251 male principals and 100 female principals of all the public junior secondary schools in Rivers State. The sample size for this study comprised of (251 male and 100 female principals) of all the public junior secondary schools in Rivers State. The instrument for the study was titled “Principals’ Fund Generation Strategy for Effective Administration Questionnaire” (PFMSEAQ). The reliability of the questionnaire instrument was established through Cronbach Alpha Method. It yielded co-efficient of 0.84. This result therefore showed internal consistency of the test items. Mean and standard deviation was used to analyze the data and answer the research questions, while z-test statistics was used to test the hypothesis at 0.5 significant levels. The agreement or disagreement of any of the item depended on the criterion mean, which are 2.50.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The research questions and hypotheses were addressed with relevant tables drawn to offer clear statistical explanation to data being analyzed.

Analysis of Data and Result Presentation

Research Question 1: What is the extent of fund generation strategy for effective administration of public junior secondary schools in Rivers State?

Table-1.1: Mean responses on fund generation strategy for effective administration of public junior secondary schools in Rivers State

(N=351 respondents)

S/N	Variables	Male Principals (n=244)		Female Principals (n=96)		MS	Decision
		\bar{x}_1	SD	\bar{x}_2	SD		
1.	Fund is provided to the school through payment of fees	3.18	1.02	2.89	1.00	3.04	HE
2.	The school generate funds through freewill donations	2.70	0.92	2.67	0.89	2.69	Moderate
3.	Through the sales of agricultural products	3.17	0.87	2.92	0.85	3.05	HE
4.	Fund generation through the sales of local crafts products	2.91	0.94	2.59	0.91	2.75	Moderate
5.	Through payment of overhead to the school	2.68	0.95	2.89	0.88	2.79	Moderate
6.	Fund generation through award winning prizes through school activities	3.26	0.72	2.65	0.92	2.96	Moderate
Grand Mean & SD		2.98	0.90	2.77	0.91	2.88	

Source: Field Survey, 2022, \bar{x} = mean; ≥ 2.50 accept, otherwise reject; SD= standard deviation

Results in table 4.1 show the extent of fund generation strategy for effective administration of public junior secondary schools in Rivers State. The results indicate that the mean scores for this subscale ranged between 2.68 (SD = 0.95) to 3.26 (SD = 0.72) for male principals, and 2.59 (SD = 0.91) to 2.92 (SD = 0.85) for female principals. The highest scored item in this subscale for male principals was fund generation through award winning prizes through school activities (Mean = 3.26; SD = 0.72), while funds through the sales of agricultural products (Mean = 2.92; SD = 0.85) was the highest scored item in this subscale for female principals. Whereas, the lowest scored item in this subscale for male principals was funds through payment of overhead to the school (Mean = 2.68; SD = 0.95), while fund generation through the sales of local crafts products (Mean = 2.59; SD = 0.91) was the lowest scored item in this subscale for female principals, respectively. This implies that the perception of both respondents on the extent of fund generation strategy for effective administration of public junior secondary schools in Rivers State varies as all the items were moderately rated

with a grand mean of 2.98 (SD = 0.90), and 2.77 (SD = 0.91), respectively for both respondents and a mean set (MS) of 2.88.

Test of Result of Hypothesis

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference between male and female principals in their mean ratings in the extent of fund generation strategy for effective administration of public junior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Table-2.1: z-Test Summary of male and female principals in their mean ratings in the extent of fund generation strategy for effective administration of public junior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Categories	n	\bar{x}_1	SD	z-cal	z-crit	Decision
Male Principals	244	2.98	0.90			
				1.92	1.96	Accept
Female Principals	96	2.77	0.91			

Table 4.7 show the summary of z-test statistics of male and female principals' on ratings in the extent of fund generation strategy for effective administration of public junior secondary schools. The result shows that the z-calculated ($Z_{cal}=1.92$) is less than the z-critical ($Z_{crit}=1.96$), therefore the hypothesis was accepted. This implies that there is no significant difference between male and female principals in their mean ratings on the extent of fund generation strategy for effective administration of public junior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Summary of the Findings

The findings of this study are presented as follows:

1. That the fund is provided to the school through payment of fees, the school generate funds through freewill donations, through the sales of agricultural products, fund generation through the sales of local crafts products, among other variables shows that male and female principals accepted that mean ratings in the extent of generation of fund strategies for effective administration of public junior secondary schools in Rivers State were moderate.
2. Hypotheses 1 revealed that $Z_{cal}=1.92$ was less than the $Z_{crit}=1.96$, therefore the hypothesis was accepted which implies that there is no significant difference between male and female principals in their mean ratings on the extent of fund generation strategies for effective administration of public junior secondary schools in Rivers State.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The result in table 1.1 above on fund generation strategy for effective administration of public junior secondary schools shows that fund is generated to the school through payment of fees, the school generate funds through freewill donations, through the sales of agricultural products, fund generation through the sales of local crafts products, among other variables shows that male and female principals accepted that mean ratings in the extent of generation of fund for effective administration of public junior secondary schools in Rivers State were moderate. This current finding is in conformity with the study of Oyewole (2006) who observed that the principal is the chief executive officer in secondary school in Nigeria. He further noted that the principal performs a good number of administrative functions in his/her effort to achieve goals and objectives which the school is meant to achieve especially in fund generation. In addition, Eziuzo (2014) noted that principals function include preparation of budget, securing revenue for the school internally and use of the fund at his disposal prudently.

Similarly, Asodike (2014) affirmed that revenue raised by the school internally to supplement grant allocation from government, but the scope of fund raising varies from one school to another, such internal sources of school funds include: enlisting help of local community, Parent Teachers Association (PTA) levies, proceeds:- from drama club; cultural dance groups; from sales of agricultural produce; from poultry/pig keeping; from sales of crafts/arts and from renting of school facilities. In addition, Ogbonnaya (2000) noted that the main purpose of financial management is the raising of funds and ensuring that the funds realized are utilized in the most effective and efficient manner. In support, Bua and Adzongo (2014) noted that poor management of fund in schools, results in; financial misappropriation, embezzlement, diversion of finance to personal issue use and negligence in school finance matters, especially issues on mismanagement of internally raised funds impacted on school financial base negatively. So generating money internally and managing same efficiently by the school head can result in improved finance for the school. Some of the sources through which fund is generated includes.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings that the principals fund generation is to a moderate extent in public junior secondary schools in Rivers State, it will be difficult for principals to achieve high performance in schools for lack of funding. This is true because internal generated fund is a boost to educational growth and development in secondary schools in Rivers State.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Principals' should collaborate with community stakeholders to initiate sources of fund to enhance the achievement of school goals and objectives.
2. The principals' should on daily bases keep adequate financial record in the school for proper accountability when the need arise. This is necessary if in case team of auditors visits the school for record purposes.
3. The government should try the much they can to allocate more funds to the junior secondary school section as there are lots of office responsibilities on the side of the principals to carry out their duties effectively.
4. There should parameters set to determine the extent of fund utilization. The parameter can be set by government of the school. It can be in a way of setting targets.
5. Record keeping should be made compulsory in school administration. To achieve this, a strong monitoring mechanism should be put in place through the State and local Boards to regularly check the operational responsibilities of the school administrators in other to ensure strict compliance on record keeping.

Contribution to Scholarship

This research exercise stands to scholarly contribute to knowledge in the following areas:

1. It will stand as literal nuggets on the principals and future researchers in related research exercise.
2. It equally stands out as ingredients of encouragement that can enhance the potentials of principals among other administrators in other sectors for maximal performance of personnel.

Suggestions for Further Studies

Based on the findings of this study the researcher made the following suggestions that:

1. Further study should be carried out on principals' fund management strategies for effective administration of public junior secondary schools in other state within Nigeria.
2. This same study on principals' fund management strategies for effective administration should be carried out using private secondary schools in the study area if similar result will be found or a contrary result.

REFERENCES

1. Ogbonnaya, N. I. (2000). Foundations of education finance. Owerri: Cape publishers LTd.
2. Okoye, E. (2014). Strategies for involving communities in the funding of secondary education in Anambra State. Unpublished Masters degree thesis submitted to the Department of Educational Foundations, Faculty of Education, Nnamdi Azikiwe University Awka.
3. Osei-Owusu and Kwame, C. K. (2015). Financing of organizations. Benin: Okperime Press.
4. Oyewole, B. K. (2006). Secondary School Administration and Maintaining quality in Nigeria educational system. Journal of Research Vocational and Technical Education 3 (1), 30-36.
5. UBE, (2012). Guidelines for realising Nigeria's millennium education Dream: The UBE. Paper presented at a seminar on stakeholders in UBE. Abuja, September 17th-20th
6. Ukpong N. N. (2019). Principals 'management of internally generated funds to enhance public secondary schools' financing for sustainable national development. International Journal of Education, Learning and Development.7, 5, 50-57.